

MEDIA LITERATE TEACHERS FOR THE FUTURE

Dr. Sheetal Yogeshchandra Deolalkar

Assistant Professor,

SSTSPM's Adhyapak Mahavidyalaya, Vadgaon Maval

Abstract –

Rapid Technological change is main characteristic of Today's world. To develop children for this brave new world will require teachers to have a mix of skills that have always been the mark of an ideal teacher. If we ask that what is the most important school based factor which influencing student performance and lifelong outcomes? We get the answer, "Teaching". So Teachers are backbone of education system.

Key words – Media, Literacy, Technology, 5A's

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Introduction –

Now a days, linguistically, culturally, socio-economically diverse school environment demands experience, empathy, inventive thinking and technological smartness of teachers. So, Strong subject knowledge, critical thinking, being a facilitator, communication, strong social skills, collaboration and creativity and many more characteristics are important for teachers. Great teachers have passion about learning, and they share and give their passion to their students. Every Child deserves access to interesting and informative teaching. For this we need talented and passionate teachers who are technologically smart. Not only this, but 'Media Literacy' is one of the main features of Modern teachers.

Objectives –

1. To know the concept of Media Literacy.
2. To know the importance of Media in Education and for teachers.
3. To discuss how media will be used by teacher in daily classroom activities.

4. To discuss Multimedia and its role in Education.

Media is a powerful force which can shape students perceptions. If the teacher is not media literate, he can't understand what the media is doing for education system. After all, it is a 21st century approach to education which provides a framework to access, analyze, evaluate and create messages in a variety of forms , from print to video to the internet. It's not a new subject in education but it is a new approach. We all know that human being recall easily what he see and do, so the power of media is basically related with these 2 activities of a person.

So to be a 'Media literate Teacher', he/she should know the 5A's. Access to media, Awareness about the power of media, Assessment of how media portray issues and events, Appreciation for the role of media which it play in creating society, and Action which encourage proper communication across cultural, social and political varied society.

To understand the process of Mass communication, to create an awareness of the impact of media on the individual and society, to acquire strategies for analyzing and discussing media messages, to enjoy understand and appreciate media content, to understand and respect the power of media messages, to create an insight into our culture and our lives, to understand ethical and moral obligations of media practitioners, and most important to know the power of media in education, we need media literacy.

So as a teacher, when you are using media think about the following points:

- What is the purpose of this message?
- Is it related with education?
- If yes, then who produced and / or paid for the message?
- What techniques are used to attract attention and increase believability?
- Does the message contain bias or stereotypes?

When you think critically as a responsible citizen and teacher about the message, you can easily develop your independent judgment about that media content.

Media Literacy Education requires active inquiry and critical thinking about the messages we receive and create. Media education is important for a teacher, through which he become media literate and able to critically understand the nature, techniques and impacts of media messages and productions. It acknowledges and builds on the positive, creative and pleasurable dimensions of popular culture.

When Media literate teacher uses and starts to literate his/her students about media and use powerful media in teaching process, he/she finds how it encourages young people to question, evaluate, understand and appreciate their multimedia culture. It teaches them to become active, engaged media consumers and users. Media education brings the world into the classroom, giving immediacy and relevance to traditional subjects such as History, English, Health, Civics and the Creative Arts. It serves as a perfect bridge for subject integration and interdisciplinary studies.

Why we need media literacy in education, because it embodies and furthers current pedagogy, which emphasizes student-centered learning, the recognition of multiple intelligences, and the analysis and management – rather than just the simple storing – of information. Not only this, but it is grounded in the sound pedagogical approach of starting learning where kids are at. The media – music, comics, television, video games, the Internet and even ads – are a part of life that all kids enjoy. Media create a shared environment and are, therefore, catalysts for learning. It helps children critique media representation, teaching them to distinguish between reality and fantasy.

When teacher and students become media literate, they understand ‘Media are constructions which are created by individuals, but keeping need and interest of people. It has commercial implications; most media production is a business and must, therefore, make a profit. Questions of ownership and control are central – a relatively small number of individuals control what we watch, read and hear in the media. Media have social & political implications. If you want to inculcate media literacy in your classroom, exploit teachable moments in your classroom, try to give a chance to your students to create media, not just analyze it, start and end your lecture with the key concepts, try to arrange and implement your lecture in the way, that kids and adults also enjoy media, and main one ‘teach about media, not just with media.’ Try to make Media education about asking questions, not learning answers, try to fight the perception that, “It doesn’t matter.”, try to assess and evaluate media literacy work, try something new which help students to bring their own media in the class and keep up-to-date with media trends and developments.

Not only media, but now a days Multimedia is a concept which emerging and increasing rapidly. Multimedia is a combination of text, graphic, sound, animation, and video that is

delivered interactively to the user by electronic or digitally manipulated means. It express with the help of words or text. But good choice of words is necessary. It could be produced manually or by computer graphics technology. It is in Audio form, Animation form, and Video form. So to be aware about Interactive Multi Media is a big task for teachers. A combination of hypertext, graphics, audio, video, (linked elements) and interactivity culminating in a complete, non-linear computer-based experience is a part of Interactive Multimedia.

Multimedia is important in Education. It is important for a teacher to know the Use and Applications of Multimedia in Education. In different courseware or simulations how it is used? What is the role of Multimedia in E-learning and distance learning? How Multimedia plays essential role in information searching? These all questions clears the important role of Multimedia in modern education.

Multimedia is an innovation in the field of education which improve the process and product of Teaching and learning. The use of many appropriate and carefully selected techniques, devices and media in such a combination as to outturn in the most effective realization of the Teaching and learning objectives in a best possible way. It referred to the use of proper and carefully selected varieties of learning experiences which are presented to the learner with the help of selected teaching strategies, will reinforce and strengthen one another in such a way that the learner will achieve predestine objectives in an effective way.

While using Multimedia when we think about the methods, it is divided in two parts; first one is Teacher initiated methods like lecture, lecture cum demonstration, historical and discussion, and second part is students initiated methods such as project, problem solving, laboratory, discovery etc. Also we have some approaches regarding use of Multimedia like factual, Conceptual, Inductive, Deductive, Constructivist, Interdisciplinary etc.

So while using this Multimedia try to use mass instructional techniques like seminar, group discussion, debate, brain storming, peer tutoring, role play and conceptual and mind mapping. But try to create two way side class environments. In which learner can proceed at his own speed or pace, try to use content in small bit of information, try to collect active responses of students, take immediate feedback, try to reinforce students and train students for self-valuation.

Conclusion –

As a future Teacher, to shape the lives of the future generation, teacher should be providing an enjoyable education experience with update media knowledge. The teacher has to learn and adopt a number of methods and techniques; he has to learn the use and application of different media, gain mastery over the use of different media, try to catch active participation of students instead of remaining passive. Teacher should design new learning experiences, has to lead his students for independent learning by using Multimedia. He has to make learning a living and co-operative process, has to play a constructive role in making his students learn the things in a practical way by giving through concrete and living experiences.

But for the effective use of Media and Multimedia in school and colleges, there is a need of sound infrastructure and needed facilities for the adoption of multimedia approach by institutions. Also, teacher needs necessary dynamicity and flexibility in the existing timetable and programmes. Proper training, setting up of proper agencies of institutes and proper changes in the attitude of teachers and learners is important.

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